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INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

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POLICY BRIEF 4

Improving migrant and refugee children
integration in Europe. Results and
lessons learned from the IMMERSE
project

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Summary

This paper is the last of a series of four policy briefs. The main aim of these documents is to link the progress and findings of the IMMERSE project to specific policy recommendations. This document analyses the results obtained from the IMMERSE large-scale survey and the lessons learned from this data collection exercise to propose policy recommendations for improving migrant and refugee children's integration in Europe.

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Results and lessons learned from the IMMERSE project

1 Summary

This paper is the last of a series of four policy briefs. The main aim of these documents is to link the progress and findings of the IMMERSE project to specific policy recommendations. This document analyses the results obtained from the IMMERSE large-scale survey and the lessons learned from this data collection exercise to propose policy recommendations for improving migrant and refugee children's integration in Europe.

2 Background

As the population of immigrant origin in Europe grows in volume, their integration and that of their descendants become a significant need for a cohesive and welcoming society.

The underage population is particularly vulnerable, especially if they have a migrant background (Ensor and Goździak, 2010), as this group generally occupies some of the lowest social positions, often with precarious administrative status (Lewis et al., 2014).

Providing a general picture of migrant children in Europe is complicated, not only because of the heterogeneity of origins and destinations but also because of the different conditions affecting such diverse groups as children who migrated, children of migrants (the so-called “second generation”), refugee minors and unaccompanied minors.

At the aggregate level, according to Eurostat, there are some 5 million foreign-born children in the EU and some 6.6 million children with foreign nationality¹. The European Labour Force Survey² indicates that in 2022, some 23 million European citizens were children of migrants, reaching, in countries such as France or Germany, around 12% of their total population, around six million in the first case and about eight million in the second. On the other hand, in the same year, some 222,100 asylum seekers in Europe were children, one-fifth of them unaccompanied minors.³ These include some of the 5.9 million Ukrainian minors who, following the outbreak of war with Russia, have proceeded to settle in the EU (UNHCR, 2023). While these aggregate statistical records provide an overall picture, national data sources must be used to obtain more specific data by groups and different characteristics. But there is no doubt that this social group of significant size and relevance has increased in the last few years.

The presence of migrant minors requires the adaptation of numerous social services, and this is mainly the case for schools and educational centres, which must face the challenge of assisting and educating a heterogeneous public with an asymmetrical educational background and, in many cases, with difficulties in speaking the language of the country of residence.

Despite the efforts of both the EU, mainly under the umbrella of the Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027) and the various Member States, the fact is that data from reports such as PISA reveal a persistent educational gap of migrant background children compared to native minors, not to mention the integration problems faced by groups such as unaccompanied minors, especially when they reach the age of majority and leave the reception system (Rodriguez et al., 2020). The IMMENSE results allow us to delve deeper into some of these aspects, thus providing a snapshot of the reality of these groups, the accuracy of which should help improve their situation.

¹ See Foreign-born population dataset (migr_pop3ctb)

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tps00178/default/table?lang=en> and the Population on 1 January by age, sex and broad group of citizenship dataset (migr_pop2ctz)

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_pop2ctz_custom_8425765/default/table?lang=en

² See population by sex, age, migration status and degree of urbanisation dataset (lfst_r_pgaum)

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/LFST_R_PGAUM/default/table?lang=en&category=labour.employ.lfst.lfst_r.lfst_r_lfurb

³ See Asylum applicants by type of applicant, citizenship, age and sex dataset (migr_asyapp)

[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctza\\$dv_618/default/table?lang=en](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctza$dv_618/default/table?lang=en)

3 Challenges to the integration of migrant minors detected by the IMMERSE survey⁴

In terms of language and culture, while the IMMERSE survey revealed that a relevant percentage of migrant-background children have a high level of competence in the language of the country of residence (73%), only 45% of them, i.e. less than half of the sample, declare feeling close to both their culture of origin and their host culture, with 44% saying that they do not feel close to their culture of origin. This may indicate a specific acculturation process, predominant among children of migrants, which should lead to a rethinking of the European intercultural framework, as an essential cultural richness that has proven to generate a double advantage for the host societies could be lost (Rumbaut and Portes, 2001). On the other hand, the fact that a not insignificant 11% of children responded that they only feel close to their culture of origin points to the need to monitor the social inclusion of a group that could, in part, fall into marginalisation.

Regarding well-being, although an immense majority reported feeling happy, as most children do, still 19% of respondents reported not feeling happy, and this proportion significantly increases with age, particularly among adolescents. In contrast, it is concerning that only 48% think that they belong to their school, which is a determining factor in children's emotional and social development in the short, medium and long term.

Friends and teachers are key players in fostering this link. Only 57% of respondents declared a great deal of support for the second, a figure that decreases as they get older, in some countries falling below 30% in the case of late adolescents. While most of these children declared trusting their schools and teachers, 12% did not trust them, and 21% were ambivalent about it. It remains necessary to strengthen an intercultural education system capable of understanding differences and building bridges between the culture of origin and that of destination.

Another essential social problem identified by the IMMERSE survey is the fact that nearly 40% of migrant children in Europe avoid certain places for fear of being mistreated and that 38% of respondents report having experienced bullying at some point. These facts reveal the importance of designing an interculturality plan that not only targets the population of migrant origin but also challenges society as a whole to educate in shared values and to eliminate racism and xenophobia from our communities. If we combine this with the fact that almost half of the schools participating in the survey (47%) do not have psychosocial support staff or student counselling services, we can identify a significant failure in preventing and mitigating the problem.

⁴ The analysed data derives from an overall aggregation of the IMMERSE survey results, whose sample sizes vary between countries. Results are thus descriptive but not statistically representative.

4 Lessons learned from carrying out research with migrant and refugee children

The results discussed above derive from a unique effort to collect large-scale data from migrant-background children across multiple European countries. Such a task was required to complement the limited available data from sources at European and national levels.

Undoubtedly, in addition to the unique data produced and now available⁵, one of the great added values of the IMMENSE survey is the experience acquired by its consortium when carrying out data collection of this magnitude with this very particular population. This section aims to maximise the knowledge assets generated in such a targeted project, transferring the lessons learned into recommendations for sustainable solutions and knowledge-based policies that benefit society. In the next section, we first present some of the challenges identified to offer recommendations to facilitate or improve some of the limitations encountered.

Firstly, as discussed above, researching the social conditions of such a vulnerable and heterogeneous group as migrant and refugee children has both ethical and logistical implications. Since each member country has its own rules regarding the role of Ethics Committees and for consent and permission for minors' participation, this makes research more agile and feasible in some contexts than others, while the GDPR always represents significant practical and technical challenges (for both digital and pen-and-paper data collection).

Secondly, the very nature of the population requires a significant effort to adapt the questionnaires to be administered in a child-friendly language and to different developmental stages. In addition, it is necessary to translate these into many other languages, given the heterogeneity of the migrant child population. The funding institutions and the research teams must be aware of these constraints when designing the work to be carried out and foresee mechanisms to add other languages and react to incoming waves and changing influxes and stocks.

Once the administrative hurdles of the participating institutions had been overcome and all the methodological tools had been designed, the consortium faced numerous structural barriers to proper data collection. Access to schools is generally mediated by the corresponding authorities (national or regional), whose role has varied between supporting, simply authorising, or straightforwardly denying (or not providing) the required authorisation for accessing schools in their jurisdiction. While understanding the need for caution and authorisation procedures in such a sensitive area, sometimes for political reasons or due to a lack of interest, surveying specific regions has not been possible. In other cases, the authorisation procedures are particularly cumbersome, lengthy, and uncertain. All of it suggests the need to activate stable channels of dialogue and cooperation between educational authorities, related research funding programs and institutions, and the actors involved in scientific research.

Despite a generalised interest in their research and goodwill, many schools contacted often faced challenges for effective participation. In addition to busy schedules, where participating in studies such as IMMENSE puts additional stress on the staff, there is often a need for more resources such

⁵ For more info, please visit <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/>

as stable internet access. Indeed, not receiving tangible rewards for participating in such research is also a critical disincentive to participation. It also loses strength because it is sporadic and not sustained over time, and so difficult to insert into the school year planning. All this leads to the fact that, in the end, school participation in this type of survey (and granted that institutional barriers are overcome) only takes place thanks to the goodwill of committed principals and teachers. Sadly, this also carries a particular risk of bias, as those actors who do not find it beneficial to participate and those who may believe that the final result will be negative may refuse to do so or have fewer incentives to participate.

Finally, this type of data collection gains momentum if it is institutionalised. The various IMMERSE teams have detected essential limits in the national statistical registers to determine where migrant pupils are and if they are enrolled in school, revealing the need to improve statistics to locate this population. This would be a necessary first step for subsequent data collection, including socio-educational dimensions such as those collected by IMMERSE. If structuralised, the regular participation of institutions and schools in collecting these vital data would allow for monitoring and then elaborating effective public policies for a population characterised by high mobility and volatility.

5 Recommended Actions

Both the results of the project and the lessons learned from its implementation have led to the elaboration of the following recommendations, which are to be considered in addition to those set out in the previous policy briefs⁶ and the project's policy recommendation documents⁷.

We recommend the European Commission to guarantee the prompt and effective implementation of the Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027). The EU should strengthen its intercultural approach, already set out in the White Paper on Intercultural Dialogue of the Council of Europe (2008), to protect cultural diversity and take advantage of it, avoiding acculturation processes.

In line with the previous proposal, we recommend that the European Commission promote the adoption of National, Regional and Local intercultural integration plans. Although the macro European approach of the action plan is much needed, social integration is a process that needs to be reinforced at each level to make it effective. In this sense, elaborating a set of EU Guidelines could guide the different administrations to vertebrate and align their plans with the Commission.

The European Commission should approve specific funds for ensuring that all schools in the EU have the means to promote the effective integration of migrant and refugee children. These funds should concretely focus, at least, on guaranteeing the availability of psychosocial or counselling

⁶ See IMMERSE Policy Brief series <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/publications/>

⁷ See IMMERSE's Policy Recommendations on refugee and migrant children integration:

<https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/policy-recommendations-on-refugee-and-migrant-children-integration/>

services, the presence of intercultural mediators and the establishment of intersectional education programs on anti-xenophobia and racism.

The EU Commission should define permanent research financing programs under the Horizon Europe umbrella and further plans to stabilise research on migrant and refugee children's conditions. With ad-hoc grants and tenders, the current design segments knowledge and impedes a longitudinal and constant action on a field whose mobility and volatility require permanent monitoring for developing practical actions. Funds should also take into account the magnitude of the work that implies surveying migrant and refugee children.

In line with the previous recommendation, IMMERSE results have proven to be an invaluable tool for policy-making, and their take-up and consideration in future EU debates and initiatives on refugee and migrant children's integration should be ensured. The European Commission should also define the mechanisms for regular data collection involving schools and reception centres systematically, as the OECD does with PISA. In contrast to PISA and other similar efforts, which are focused on academic skills and particular populations, equivalent programs are also needed for deepening different relevant dimensions of socio-educational integration and child development to dispose of reliable and constant data, allowing monitor the evolution of the socio-educational integration indicators developed by IMMERSE.

6 Conclusions

Although the results of the IMMERSE survey show a relatively positive picture of the integration of migrant and refugee children in Europe, as this Policy Brief has highlighted, some dimensions show the need to take measures to tackle and also prevent problems of different nature: from marginalisation to acculturation and lack of psychosocial support. The unique data collection exercise has also provided valuable lessons of utmost importance. Taking up these lessons and the derived recommendations may set the basis for establishing a more transparent, effective and open context for researching on migrant and refugee children integration. Identifying the most relevant challenges affecting this population is essential for designing successful policies that can make a difference in shaping more inclusive and cohesive European societies.

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